

Remote Device Control

Remote device control is an integral part of device integration. The device integration protocol generally enables remote access and data transfer. These can be set up separately, with neither relying on the other. In this guideline, we have mainly discussed the configurations for remote data or device access.

Users will be able to access the device through the Chemotion ELN. For that, we must ensure that the device PC and the Chemotion ELN are connected to a common LAN. Furthermore, the firewall of the LAN needs to allow VNC connections to be established.

Configurations in source PC

This has been achieved by the installation of the software, [TightVNC](#) (Installer for Windows, 64-bit). Users can access the computer remotely through Chemotion ELN through this. We have to configure it as follows,

On the setup screen, we have to select the TightVNC server to be installed along with the setup of the passwords for remote access and administrative password.

After installation, we have to make sure it is accepting incoming connections at port 5900, and also for added security, we have to whitelist the IP address of the Chemotion ELN only. Also, we select the option so that the administrative password is needed to make any changes or for each operation.

TightVNC Service Configuration

Server | Extra Ports | Access Control | Video | Administration

Incoming Viewer Connections

- Accept incoming connections
- Main server port: 5900
- Require VNC authentication
- Primary password:
Change... Unset
- View-only password:
Set... Unset

Web Access

- Serve Java Viewer to Web clients
- Web access port: 5800

Input Handling

- Block remote input events
- Block remote input on local activity
- Inactivity: 3 sec
- No local input during client sessions

Miscellaneous

- Enable file transfers
- Hide desktop wallpaper
- Show icon in the notification area
- Connect to RDP session

Update Handling

- Use D3D driver if available
- Use mirror driver if available
- Screen polling cycle: 1000 ms

OK Cancel Apply

Configurations in Chemotion ELN

There are two types of configurations we have to perform in Chemotion ELN,

- As an admin of Chemotion ELN
- As an admin of the group to which the device belongs

As an admin of Chemotion ELN, we have to create the device corresponding to the target device and configure the NoVNC settings for it with a token.

On the other hand, as an admin of the group which the device belongs to, we have to make sure that the user belongs to the group in Chemotion ELN in order to get access to the device. If

the user is not already in the group, then the group admin will have to add the user from Chemotion ELN.

For a user who is in the group, the user has to log in to the Chemotion ELN at <https://complat-eln.ioc.kit.edu/home>. Then he can access the device as follows,

For further information regarding the VNC settings, see the [VNC settings page](#)